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Determination of Metal Contents in Pollen Samples Collected From Different Regions in Turkey

E. Yarsan¹, S. Sevin^{1*}, H. Ekici², Y. Aluç³ and G. Akdeniz⁴

¹ Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Ankara University Veterinary Medicine, 06110, Ankara, Turkey

² Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Kirikkale University Veterinary Medicine, 71450, Kirikkale, Turkey

³ Directorate of Scientific and Technological Research Center, Kirikkale University, 71450, Kirikkale, Turkey

⁴ Apiculture Research Institute, Republic Of Turkey Ministry Of Agriculture And Forestry, 52200, Ordu, Turkey

*Corresponding author: E-mail: sedatsevin59@gmail.com, Tel +90 312 317 03 15, Fax: +90 312 316 44 72

Abstract

Beekeeping is considered one of the most important agricultural activities around the world. Turkey has important place among the honey producer countries, it is placed the 2nd (for bee hives) and 2th, position among the honey producing countries in the world. In Turkey, there are about 8 million bee hives producing about 105,000 million tons of honeys. Although all regions of Turkey are suitable for apiculture, the Aegean, Black Sea, and Mediterranean regions are considered to be the most important. Pollen is an important food for humans. Its importance is not only nutritional, but it is also a bio-indicator for environmental pollution. Bees fly intensively in a radius of up to 5 km, and for this reason they and their products can serve as bio-indicators for the contamination of the area. A number of authors have used honey bees and/or their products for monitoring environmental pollution. Air and water contain heavy metals from industry and traffic, which can contaminate the bee colonies and their products. Factories, industrial organizations, environmental waste incineration and high automobile traffic congestion situations like can lead to the release of the following metals: aluminum, copper, iron, lead, magnesium, silicon, zinc, barium, cadmium, chromium, nickel, palladium, platinum. The aim of this study is to evaluate some metal (Al, Co, Cu, Fe, Mg, Mn, Ni, Pb and Zn) contents of pollens, collected from different regions (Marmara, Aegean, Black Sea, Mediterranean, Central Anatolia, Eastern Anatolia) of Turkey.

In this study the concentrations of some elements in 29 pollen samples were investigated. Samples were obtained from beekeepers. The levels of Al, Co, Cu, Fe, Mg, Mn, Ni, Pb and Zn elements in pollen samples were determined by ICP-OES instrument. The samples were digested in microwave oven using nitric acid and hydrogen peroxide. The mean concentration of elements and the lowest and highest values were determined. As a result of analysis, the concentration of elements in pollen samples were detected as 67,32±45,08 ppb, 0,01±0,02 ppb, 7,12±1,33 ppb, 108,59±60,62 ppb, 491,82±108,25 ppb, 23,66±14,38 ppb, 1,01±0,82 ppb, 0,31±0,13 ppb and 20,56±4,79 ppb, for Al, Co, Cu, Fe, Mg, Mn, Ni, Pb and Zn respectively. To conclude, the concentrations of detected heavy metals in collected pollen samples were below the maximum residue limits of some international residue limits. Therefore, it would not pose a risk to human health. This study can contribute other studies, which will be carried out in other regions and provinces, in the determination of possible element concentrations in pollen. Research on this subject are important in terms of public health.

Keywords: Bee product, bio-indicator, environmental pollution, metals, pollen